

PREVISÃO DE DESLIZAMENTOS POR MEIO DE TÉCNICAS DE APRENDIZADO DE MÁQUINA: UMA REVISÃO SISTEMÁTICA DA LITERATURA

PREDICTING LANDSLIDES THROUGH MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW¹

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RESUMO

Revisões sistemáticas são fundamentais para sintetizar evidências e identificar lacunas científicas. Este estudo analisa 87 artigos de periódicos de alto impacto da base Scopus que abordaram o mapeamento de suscetibilidade a deslizamentos (*landslide susceptibility mapping* - LSM) através de aprendizado de máquina (*machine learning* - ML). A revisão sintetiza os modelos utilizados, fatores de influência e abordagens metodológicas. Os algoritmos mais frequentes são *Support Vector Machines (SVM)*, *Random Forest (RF)*, and *Logistic Regression (LR)*, empregados em 40%, 31% e 23% dos estudos analisados, respectivamente. Entre os principais fatores associados aos deslizamentos estão declive (94%), aspecto (92%), elevação (87%), distância aos cursos d'água (79%) e uso e cobertura da terra (74%). Os resultados evidenciam a crescente aplicação do ML no LSM, contribuindo para maior precisão preditiva e tomada de decisão informada na gestão de risco de deslizamentos. Deste modo, este estudo fornece insights valiosos sobre tendências atuais, avanços metodológicos e futuras direções de pesquisa em previsão de deslizamentos.

Palavras-Chave: Avaliação de risco de deslizamentos. Análise baseada em dados. Modelagem geoespacial. Métodos de mapeamento de risco. Avaliação de fatores ambientais.

ABSTRACT

Systematic literature reviews are essential for synthesizing scientific evidence and identifying research gaps. This study analyzes 87 articles from high-impact journals in the Scopus database that addressed landslide susceptibility mapping (LSM) through machine learning (ML). The review summarizes the most used models, influencing factors, and methodological approaches. The most frequently applied algorithms are Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and Logistic Regression (LR), employed in 40%, 31% and 23% of the analyzed studies, respectively. The most significant landslide factors include slope (94%), aspect (92%), elevation (87%), distance to rivers (79%), and land use/land cover (LULC) (74%). The results highlight the increasing integration of ML in LSM, contributing to enhanced predictive accuracy and informed decision-making in landslide risk management. In this way, this study provides valuable insights into current trends, methodological advancements, and future research directions in landslide prediction.

Keywords: Landslide hazard assessment. Data-driven analysis. Geospatial modeling. Risk mapping methods. Environmental factor evaluation.

¹ This review served as the foundational basis for the study "[Insights into Landslide Susceptibility: A Comparative Evaluation of Multi-Criteria Analysis and Machine Learning Techniques.](#)"

1 INTRODUCTION

Literature reviews play an essential role in academic research, allowing scholars to evaluate existing knowledge, identify research gaps, and synthesize findings to test hypotheses or develop new theories (Xiao and Watson, 2019). A systematic literature review is an organized method for searching, collecting, and evaluating scientific evidence related to a hypothesis, serving as a fundamental tool across various fields of knowledge (Letouze *et al.*, 2016). As the primary method for generating scientific evidence, systematic literature reviews compile the highest-quality studies on a given research topic (Kitchenham *et al.*, 2009). Hence, systematic reviews serve as a methodological approach to consolidating evidence on a particular research question, providing valuable insights for policymakers, practitioners, researchers, and the general public (Shrikant, 2024). Thus, a comprehensive literature review on landslide susceptibility mapping (LSM) provides valuable insights into methodologies for developing and applying susceptibility models, guiding the selection of an appropriate statistical model, performance evaluation, and uncertainty estimation (Reichenbach *et al.*, 2018).

Recent advancements in technologies such as remote sensing (RS), geographic information systems (GIS), and machine learning (ML) have been increasingly applied in LSM, where RS is primarily used for data extraction in target regions and GIS for collecting, storing, managing, processing, analyzing, and visualizing georeferenced data (Erener and Düzgün, 2012; Merghadi *et al.*, 2020; Nhu *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, GIS provides essential tools for generating maps and inventories, predicting scenarios, and assessing hazards, vulnerabilities, and risks related to both natural and anthropogenic disasters (Indirli, 2009). In parallel, ML techniques have gained increasing prominence in LSM, as numerous models based on various statistical approaches have demonstrated strong predictive capabilities across diverse regions (Merghadi *et al.*, 2020; Ullah *et al.*, 2025). Thus, the widespread adoption of these techniques has contributed to enhancing the accuracy of LSM by enabling the efficient generation of reliable maps when provided with sufficient high-quality data, ultimately supporting better predictions and improved decision-making in landslide risk management (Liu *et al.*, 2023). In this sense, this study aims to conduct a systematic literature review on LSM through ML techniques, providing a comprehensive understanding of how these innovative technologies are being used in landslide prediction. It is expected that our results will contribute to a deeper insight into the potential of ML in LSM, offering valuable guidance for future research and practical applications in the field of geohazard management.

2 METHODS

Conducting a systematic literature review requires establishing a study protocol that defines a detailed review plan, outlines the process to be followed, and minimizes potential biases in research (Brereton *et al.*, 2007). This protocol should encompass key elements such as the search methodology, criteria for article inclusion and exclusion, study quality assessment, result accuracy evaluation, and the selection of appropriate statistical analysis methods (Sampaio and Mancini, 2007). Building upon this framework, our study adopts a methodology adapted from Atallah & Castro (1998), Letouze *et al.* (2016) and Sampaio & Mancini (2007). This approach followed a structured, seven-step methodology. The first step involved formulating a clear scientific question: "Which studies have applied machine learning techniques to landslide susceptibility mapping?" In the second step, relevant keywords were

defined, with “Machine Learning,” “Landslide Susceptibility,” and “Geographic Information System” selected to guide the search. The third step consisted of selecting the database, with Scopus chosen due to its comprehensive coverage of high-quality scientific literature.

In the fourth step, a rigorous screening process was applied to the search results. This included an initial filtering based on titles and abstracts, followed by a full-text review to ensure the inclusion of only highly relevant studies. The fifth step involved systematically organizing key characteristics of the selected studies into a structured table. The sixth step entailed a quantitative analysis of the dataset, categorizing the studies by publication year, country, continent, journal, publisher, and research domain. Finally, a qualitative synthesis (step seven) was conducted to identify prevailing research trends, methodological patterns, and critical knowledge gaps. This systematic and reproducible methodology ensured a comprehensive and insightful synthesis of the current literature (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Flowchart of the systematic literature review process.

Source: Adapted from Atallah & Castro (1998), Letouze et al. (2016) and Sampaio & Mancini (2007).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following the methodology outlined in the previous section, a total of 117 documents were initially retrieved from the Scopus database. Applying the defined inclusion criteria, the selection process prioritized studies published in high-impact, peer-reviewed journals. After a rigorous screening and eligibility assessment, 87 articles were retained for the final systematic review (Figure 2). Notably, most of these studies (68%) were published in Q1-ranked journals according to Scopus, underscoring the scientific rigor and relevance of the selected literature.

Figure 2. Studies included in the systematic literature review.

n = number of studies included in each step.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Although no publication date restrictions were imposed, all identified articles were published from 2015 onward. A clear upward trend in research activity was observed over time, with a marked increase in the number of publications. Notably, 2021 recorded the highest number of articles published within the analyzed period, reflecting growing scholarly interest in the application of ML to LSM (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Number of publications by year.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Figure 4a presents the geographical distribution of the studies included in this analysis, highlighting a strong concentration of research efforts in Asia. Notably, 92% of the articles originated from this continent, with China (26%), India (25%), and Vietnam (14%) emerging as the most frequently represented countries (Figure 4b).

Figure 4. Percentage of included articles by continent (a).
 Percentage of included articles by country (b).

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

The selected articles were categorized according to their primary publishers and associated research domains, as illustrated in Figures 5a and 5b. Most publications (84%) were issued by three major publishers: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI), Elsevier, and Springer. Similarly, a substantial proportion (91%) of the studies were linked to

the fields of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Environmental Science, and Computer Science (Figure 5b).

Figure 5. Number of included articles by publisher (a) and research domain (b).

*Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI); IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters (IEEE); National Institute of Science Communication and Information Resources (NISCAIR).
 Source: Elaborated by the authors.

The 87 articles included in the review were published across 34 different journals. However, Catena (Elsevier), Environmental Earth Sciences (Springer), and Remote Sensing (MDPI) accounted for 30% of the publications. Figure 6 highlights all journals that were represented by more than one publication.

Figure 6. Number of included articles by journals.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Figure 7 presents the main algorithms and techniques employed in landslide susceptibility prediction based on the reviewed studies. The three most frequently applied methods were Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and Logistic Regression (LR), reported in 35 (40%), 27 (31%), and 20 (23%) articles, respectively. Among these, SVM emerged as the most widely employed ML model, a finding consistent with observations from previous studies (Merghadi *et al.*, 2020; Ado *et al.*, 2022; Tehrani *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 7. Most employed algorithms and techniques in LSM.

* Support Vector Machines (SVM); Random Forest (RF), Logistic regression (LR), Artificial Neural Network (ANN); Rotation Forest (RTF), Decision Tree (DT); Naïve Bayes (NB); Logistic Model Trees (LMT); Random Subspace (RS); Bayesian Network (BN); K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN); Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM); Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO); Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS); Kernel Logistic Regression (KLR); Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP); Naïve-Bayes Tree (NBT); Alternative Decision Tree (ADTree); Radial Basis Function (RBF); Functional trees (FT); Classification and Regression Tree (CART); Boosted Regression Tree (BRT).

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Figure 8 depicts the key landslide conditioning factors identified across the reviewed studies, focusing on those cited more than twice. The five most frequently reported factors were slope, aspect, elevation, distance to rivers, and land use/land cover (LULC), mentioned in 82 (94%), 80 (92%), 76 (87%), 69 (79%), and 64 (74%) studies, respectively. These findings are consistent with those of Dias *et al.* (2021), who also highlighted slope, aspect, and elevation as the most commonly utilized factors in LSM.

Figure 8. Main landslides causative factors.

*Land use / land cover (LULC); Topographic Wetness Index (TWI); Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI); Stream Power Index (SPI); Topographic Ruggedness Index (TRI); Sediment Transport Index (STI); Terrain Position Index (TPI); Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA); Normalized Difference Building Index (NDBI); Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI).

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Figure 9 shows the distribution of studies based on the number of landslide conditioning factors considered. Among the included articles, 28% incorporated fewer than 10 factors, 46% included between 10 and 15 factors, 21% considered 15 to 20 factors, and only 5% utilized more than 20 factors in their analyses.

Figure 9. Distribution of landslide influencing factors considered in the included articles.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Except for two studies, all included articles reported the use of a landslide inventory to support model assessment. These inventories were generally classified into four categories: image interpretation, field surveys, historical records, and previous studies. Image interpretation typically involves the analysis of aerial photographs and satellite imagery, while historical records are usually obtained from governmental agencies. The category of previous studies encompasses data derived from academic or independent research not necessarily affiliated with official institutions. As illustrated in Figure 10, 39 studies (45%) employed a combination of image interpretation, field surveys, and historical records in their analyses.

Figure 10. Categorization of landslide inventory sources applied in the included article.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

To assess the performance of landslide prediction models, 85 of the included articles (98%) employed the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, as shown in Figure 11. Additional statistical evaluation metrics—such as mean error, mean absolute error, and root mean square error—were used in 33 studies (38%). The Kappa index was applied in 15 studies (17%), while accuracy (ACC) and sensitivity were reported in 14 studies (16%). These findings align with previous research indicating that the ROC Area Under the Curve (AUC) is the most widely adopted metric for evaluating the performance of ML algorithms in LSM (Dias *et al.*, 2021; Ado *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 11. Metrics of the performance evaluation used to assess landslide prediction models.

* Mean error, mean absolute error and root mean square error.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND LIMITATIONS

This systematic review provides a comprehensive synthesis of recent research on the application of ML techniques for LSM. A total of 87 peer-reviewed articles published between 2015 and 2021 were analyzed to identify prevailing methodological trends, key influencing factors, and evaluation practices within the field. The results highlight a growing interest in ML-based approaches to LSM, with a sharp increase in publications over the last decade, particularly in 2021.

SVM, RF and LR emerged as the most frequently used algorithms, with SVM identified as the dominant technique across the reviewed literature. Similarly, slope, aspect, elevation, distance to rivers, and LULC were the most employed conditioning factors. Notably, most studies utilized between 10 and 15 influencing factors, demonstrating a preference for moderate model complexity.

Asia, particularly China, India, and Vietnam, accounted for most of the research output, indicating a regional concentration of scientific efforts likely driven by the high incidence of landslide events and data availability in these areas. Moreover, most studies relied on landslide inventories generated through a combination of image interpretation, field surveys, and historical records, which underscores the importance of multi-source data integration in improving model reliability. For model evaluation, the ROC AUC metric was employed by the vast majority of studies, reaffirming its widespread acceptance as a robust and reliable tool for measuring the predictive performance of algorithms applied to LSM.

Despite offering valuable insights into current trends and methodologies in LSM, this review is not without limitations. Firstly, the analysis was limited to articles indexed in the Scopus database, which, although comprehensive, may have excluded relevant studies from other databases or sources. Secondly, the identification of relevant literature is generally

influenced by the selection of keywords, which may have inadvertently constrained the scope and comprehensiveness of the review. Furthermore, the manual screening and categorization of articles proved to be both time-consuming and complex, particularly given the methodological diversity across studies.

Another important limitation relates to the variability in the datasets, spatial resolutions, and validation techniques employed, which hindered a consistent comparison of the predictive accuracy of different ML models across similar study areas. Additionally, the predominance of studies originating from a limited number of countries, especially from Asia, may affect the generalizability of findings to regions with different geomorphological or socio-environmental contexts.

The standardization of landslide causative factors also posed a methodological challenge, as terminological inconsistencies across studies complicated comparative analysis. To overcome these constraints, future reviews could benefit from the integration of text mining tools and automated data extraction techniques to enhance efficiency, consistency, and reproducibility in the review process. Overall, despite these limitations, this study highlights the growing significance of ML techniques in improving the accuracy of landslide prediction and reinforces their potential for supporting more effective risk management and mitigation strategies.

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